

Comparison of pressure and displacement formulations for finite elements in linear time-harmonic acoustics

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Abstract

In this article, we compare the finite element solution of the pressure and the displacement formulations **for the acoustic problem in the frequency domain**. The Helmholtz differential equation is solved for **both, the spectral and the source problems, and each of these is formulated in terms of pressure and displacement**. The pressure formulation allows to use standard Lagrangian elements whereas Raviart-Thomas elements **applied for** the displacement formulation. Both formulations are tested in several examples. It is shown that Raviart-Thomas elements account for a reasonable alternative to Lagrangian elements in some cases.

Key words: Raviart-Thomas elements, source problem, spectral problem

1. INTRODUCTION

Mathematical modelling of the noise problem in the frequency domain has already been thoroughly studied. In general, the equations are written in terms of pressure variation in the fluid domain, resulting in the well-known Helmholtz equation. An alternative, much less explored, is to write the equations by means on the displacement of the particles. This second case adds an obvious difficulty: the unknown is vectorial, so, apparently, the number of degrees of freedom that result when discretizing this problem will be much higher than in the first case. Anyway, the use of the displacement (or, equivalently, the velocity) can be of practical interest in some cases (for example, if our measuring devices are calibrated according to one of these unknowns). Moreover,

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if we use a suitable discretization (an overview of different types of finite elements can be seen in [8]), the number of degrees of freedom can be not to larger than in the pressure case.

In this work we will study both formulations, but we will use two different types of finite elements: The pressure formulation (scalar magnitude) will be discretized by using Lagrangian elements meanwhile Raviart-Thomas elements [18] will be used for the displacement formulation (vectorial magnitude). In both cases, first, second and third order elements will be considered. We will provide computational examples for both cases, for two and three-dimensional test cases, and considering triangular and quadrilateral meshes (respectively, in 3D, tetrahedral and hexahedral meshes). We will use unstructured meshes for all computations. The numerical codes that we have used to obtain these results have been implemented in `COMSOL Multiphysics 3.4` [9].

Regarding the displacement formulation, it is important to emphasize that, in principle, Lagrangian elements could apply to this formulation as well. But, in this case, it is known that they produce spurious modes [10]. These spurious modes appear because Lagrange finite elements do not approximate correctly the rotational modes, which fill up the infinite dimensional kernel of the displacement formulation. On the contrary, Raviart-Thomas elements are able to deal with these rotational modes, as can be seen in [5, 6, 3]. In these references, Raviart-Thomas elements have been proved to be useful for fluid-structure interaction problems when both, structural and fluid vibrations, are described in terms of displacement, in which case the system matrices of the coupled problem remain symmetric.

The outline of this article is as follows: Section 2 presents the statement of the problem, showing the two formulations for the acoustic problems (source and spectral) that we will consider. In Section 3, the finite element formulations for the pressure and displacement formulations are presented for Lagrangian elements and for Raviart-Thomas elements, respectively. In section 4 we present two-dimensional examples: an eigenvalue problem in a rectangular domain and a source problem for a domain representing the interior of a car [1, 19]. In Section 5 we present three-dimensional examples: first, the eigenvalue problems encompass a parallelepipedical domain; second, a source problem what can be understood as traveling waves in a duct, where one end is excited by applying a particle velocity and waves are absorbed at the opposite end [12, 13, 14]; third, the spectral problem for a non academical example, where the interior domain of an urban bus is considered. Finally, conclusions are presented in Section 6.

2. Statement of the problem

2.1. Acoustic equations

Let Ω be a bounded domain of \mathbb{R}^2 or \mathbb{R}^3 . We denote its boundary by Γ , which can be divided into two parts, Γ_1 and Γ_2 , as shown in Figure 1. The outer normal unit vector is given by \mathbf{n} .

Figure 1: Domain of the problem.

We assume that Ω is filled with a compressible and inviscid fluid. Then, if \mathbf{U} denotes the displacement field and if we neglect internal forces, the linearized equation of motion of such a fluid can be written as (see [15])

$$\rho_0 \ddot{\mathbf{U}} - \nabla (\rho_0 c_0^2 \operatorname{div} \mathbf{U}) = \mathbf{0}, \quad (1)$$

where ρ_0 is the pressure, c_0 the speed of sound in the fluid, and the dot represents the time derivative.

We define the Lagrangian fluctuation of the pressure, with respect to a reference configuration, as

$$P := -\rho_0 c_0^2 \operatorname{div} \mathbf{U}. \quad (2)$$

Assuming ρ_0 and c_0 to be constant, we obtain by evaluating the divergence of the relation (1)

$$\frac{1}{c_0^2} \ddot{P} - \Delta P = 0, \quad \text{in } \Omega. \quad (3)$$

If we assume that all excitation of this system is time-harmonic as $e^{-i\omega t}$, then the linearity of the problems implies that the solution shows the same stationary behaviour. Thus, equations (1)

and (3) turn to

$$-\omega^2 \rho_0 \mathbf{u} - \nabla (\rho_0 c_0^2 \operatorname{div} \mathbf{u}) = \mathbf{0}, \quad \text{in } \Omega, \quad (4)$$

$$-\frac{\omega^2}{c_0^2} p - \Delta p = 0, \quad \text{in } \Omega, \quad (5)$$

respectively. From equations (2) and (4) we obtain the following relation between pressure and displacements in the frequency domain

$$\mathbf{u} = \frac{1}{\omega^2 \rho_0} \nabla p, \quad \text{in } \Omega, \quad (6)$$

which implies

$$\mathbf{u} \cdot \mathbf{n} = \frac{1}{\omega^2 \rho_0} \frac{\partial p}{\partial \mathbf{n}}, \quad \text{on } \Gamma. \quad (7)$$

2.2. Source problems

By using the equations in the previous subsection and fixing boundary conditions on Γ_1 and Γ_2 , we obtain two equivalent harmonic source problems, which correspond to the acoustic fluid equations written in terms of pressure and displacement, respectively,

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{ll} \Delta p + \frac{\omega^2}{c_0^2} p = 0, & \text{in } \Omega, \\ p = h, & \text{on } \Gamma_1, \\ \frac{\partial p}{\partial \mathbf{n}} = g, & \text{on } \Gamma_2, \end{array} \right. \quad (8)$$

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{ll} \nabla (\rho_0 c_0^2 \operatorname{div} \mathbf{u}) + \omega^2 \rho_0 \mathbf{u} = \mathbf{0} & \text{in } \Omega, \\ \operatorname{div} \mathbf{u} = -\frac{1}{\rho_0 c_0^2} h, & \text{on } \Gamma_1, \\ \mathbf{u} \cdot \mathbf{n} = \frac{1}{\omega^2 \rho_0} g, & \text{on } \Gamma_2, \end{array} \right. \quad (9)$$

where h and g are given functions.

We want to emphasize that usually only the first problem (8) is taken into consideration for acoustical studies. Clearly, problem (8) has many advantages over (9): the unknown is scalar, its variational formulation corresponds to the classical and well studied Helmholtz problem (as we will see in Section 2.4) and it can be reliably discretized by standard Lagrangian elements. However, the results of Sections 4 and 5 will show that the displacement formulation, when solved adequately by

using Raviart-Thomas elements (see Section 3.2), can be a real alternative to the standard pressure formulation.

2.3. Spectral problems

Furthermore, we deal with the spectral problems related to the source problems (8) and (9). The solution of spectral problems aims at finding real frequencies and non-null functions satisfying the corresponding equation for homogeneous boundary values, i.e.:

Find $\omega \in \mathbb{R}$ and $p \neq 0$ such that

$$\begin{cases} \Delta p + \frac{\omega^2}{c_0^2} p = 0, & \text{in } \Omega, \\ p = 0, & \text{on } \Gamma_1, \\ \frac{\partial p}{\partial \mathbf{n}} = 0, & \text{on } \Gamma_2. \end{cases} \quad (10)$$

Find $\omega \in \mathbb{R}$ and $\mathbf{u} \neq \mathbf{0}$ such that

$$\begin{cases} \nabla (\rho_0 c_0^2 \operatorname{div} \mathbf{u}) + \omega^2 \rho_0 \mathbf{u} = \mathbf{0} & \text{in } \Omega, \\ \operatorname{div} \mathbf{u} = 0, & \text{on } \Gamma_1, \\ \mathbf{u} \cdot \mathbf{n} = 0, & \text{on } \Gamma_2. \end{cases} \quad (11)$$

Clearly, the spectral problems (10) and (11) represent pressure and displacement formulations, respectively.

2.4. Variational formulations

The variational formulations are easily found after setting up the residuals and integrating by parts. Test functions q and \mathbf{v} are introduced for the pressure and the displacement formulation, respectively, in order to obtain the following weak source problems:

Find p such that $p|_{\Gamma_1} = h$ and

$$\int_{\Omega} \nabla p \cdot \nabla q - \frac{\omega^2}{c_0^2} \int_{\Omega} p q = \int_{\Gamma_2} g q, \quad \forall q \text{ such that } q|_{\Gamma_1} = 0. \quad (12)$$

Find \mathbf{u} such that $\mathbf{u} \cdot \mathbf{n} = \frac{1}{\omega^2 \rho_0} g$ on Γ_2 and

$$\int_{\Omega} \operatorname{div} \mathbf{u} \operatorname{div} \mathbf{v} - \frac{\omega^2}{c_0^2} \int_{\Omega} \mathbf{u} \cdot \mathbf{v} = - \int_{\Gamma_1} \frac{1}{\rho_0 c_0^2} h(\mathbf{x}) \mathbf{v} \cdot \mathbf{n}, \quad \forall \mathbf{v} \text{ such that } \mathbf{v} \cdot \mathbf{n} = 0 \text{ on } \Gamma_2. \quad (13)$$

Moreover, the variational formulation of spectral problems (10) and (11) are, respectively,
Find $\omega \in \mathbb{R}$ and $p \neq 0$ such that

$$\int_{\Omega} \nabla p \cdot \nabla q = \frac{\omega^2}{c_0^2} \int_{\Omega} pq, \quad \forall q \text{ such that } q|_{\Gamma_1} = 0. \quad (14)$$

Find $\omega \in \mathbb{R}$ and $\mathbf{u} \neq \mathbf{0}$ such that

$$\int_{\Omega} \operatorname{div} \mathbf{u} \operatorname{div} \mathbf{v} = \frac{\omega^2}{c_0^2} \int_{\Omega} \mathbf{u} \cdot \mathbf{v}, \quad \forall \mathbf{v} \text{ such that } \mathbf{v} \cdot \mathbf{n} = 0 \text{ on } \Gamma_2. \quad (15)$$

3. Finite element discretization

In order to solve the variational problems numerically, we will use two different types of finite elements: Lagrangian elements for the pressure formulation and Raviart-Thomas elements for the displacement formulation. Both formulations will be tested by using first, second and third order elements. Triangular and quadrilateral elements will be used as well as tetrahedral and hexahedral shapes for two-dimensional and three-dimensional problems, respectively.

3.1. Lagrangian elements for pressure formulations

As it is standard for gradient-type problems, we will approximate the solution p of (12) and (14) by using Lagrangian elements,

$$p(\mathbf{x}) \cong \sum_{i=1}^{M_p} \xi_i q_i(\mathbf{x}).$$

Here M_p corresponds to the number of nodes in the mesh and q_i are the linear, quadratic or third order Lagrangian interpolation functions which take the value 1 at node i and 0 at the other nodes. The values ξ_i represent the values of the pressure at each node.

3.2. Raviart-Thomas elements for displacement formulations

It is well known that Lagrangian elements are not suited for solving the displacement problems (13) and (15) since they suffer from the presence of spurious modes resulting from a wrong representation of the rotational modes (see, for example, [10]). A number of different techniques is known to overcome this problem. Among them, the use of Raviart-Thomas elements has proved to be successful (see [5, 6]).

The Raviart-Thomas space, \mathbf{RT}_k , is set up by vectorial functions of order k whose general form in an element K is (see [2, 7, 11])

$$\mathbf{RT}_k(K) = [p_{k-1}(K)]^N + \mathbf{x} [p_{k-1}(K)] , \quad (16)$$

where N is the dimension of the domain (2 or 3) and p_{k-1} is an arbitrary polynomial of degree $k-1$.

From this definition it can be seen (see [7]) that the degrees of freedom of \mathbf{RT}_k in the mesh depend on the integral of the normal component on the boundary of each element and on the integral of all the functions inside the elements,

$$\int_{\partial K} \mathbf{v} \cdot \mathbf{n} p_k ds, \quad \int_K \mathbf{v} \cdot \mathbf{p}_{k-1} d\mathbf{x}.$$

Then, for a given mesh, if \mathbf{v}_i is the \mathbf{RT}_k function that is 1 in one of these d.o.f. and 0 in the others, we approximate the solution \mathbf{u} of problems (13) and (15) by a linear combination of such basis functions,

$$\mathbf{u} \approx \sum_{i=1}^{M_d} \xi_i \mathbf{v}_i,$$

where M_d is the total number of d.o.f. in the mesh for the Raviart-Thomas elements.

4. Two-dimensional examples

4.1. Eigenvalues of a rectangular domain

As a first test case, we consider the spectral problem for a rectangular domain with boundary condition $\frac{\partial p}{\partial \mathbf{n}} = 0$ on Γ (it is, according to the notation in Section 2.3, $\Gamma_2 = \Gamma$).

In this case, by performing a separation of variables, it can easily be found (see [5]) that the exact eigenvalues are

$$\omega_{mn} = c_0 \pi \sqrt{\left(\frac{m}{L_x}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{n}{L_y}\right)^2} \text{ rad/s}, \quad \text{with } m, n = 0, 1, 2, \dots, \quad (17)$$

where L_x and L_y are the edge lengths of the domain.

In our numerical experiments, we use a domain with lengths $L_x = 1\text{m}$ and $L_y = 1.2\text{m}$, respectively. The acoustic fluid is air, i.e., $\rho_0 = 1\text{ kg/m}^3$ and $c_0 = 340\text{ m/s}$.

We compare the convergence of the third, the fourth and the fifth eigenvalue. Note that the first eigenvalue of this problem is zero. In all cases, this eigenvalue has been reproduced exactly by the numerical formulations. The second mode, the 01-mode ($m = 0, n = 1$) represents a vertical half wave, analogous to the horizontal half wave of mode three, i.e. the 10-mode. It was not considered in detail here since its behavior is similar to the behavior of the third mode. The fourth and the fifth eigenvalues represent the 11-mode and the 02-mode, respectively. In Figure 2, we show the sound pressure distribution of the corresponding modes.

Figure 2: Rectangular domain: Sound pressure distribution for the third, fourth and the fifth eigenvector, respectively.

Figures 3, 4 and 5 show the convergence behaviour of the second, the third and the fourth eigenvalues, respectively. The relative percental error,

$$error_{mn} = \left| \frac{\omega_{mn_{exact}} - \omega_{mn}}{\omega_{mn_{exact}}} \right| \cdot 100\%, \quad (18)$$

is plotted versus the number of degrees of freedom, for triangular (left subfigures) and quadrilateral meshes (right subfigures).

It can be seen that, for quadrilateral elements, Lagrangian elements produce better results than Raviart-Thomas elements of the same order. Regarding triangular meshes, \mathbf{RT}_1 gives better results than P_1 , almost identical error curves are found for second order elements and P_3 performs better than \mathbf{RT}_3 .

4.2. 2d example of the source problem

As a second test we consider the source problem with non homogeneous boundary conditions in a non academic domain (see Figure 6), representing a 2d cut of the interior of a car. The geometry is

Figure 3: Rectangular domain: Error curves for the third eigenvalue. Triangular meshes on the left and quadrilateral meshes on the right.

Figure 4: Rectangular domain: Error curves for the fourth eigenvalue. Triangular meshes on the left and quadrilateral meshes on the right.

taken from [19] and was used as a test example for identification of boundary admittance conditions in [1].

We assume that there is an arbitrary point source acting outside the domain, $\mathbf{x}_0 \notin \Omega \cup \Gamma$, and we further assume that the transmission through the boundary is perfect. This results in the problem

$$\begin{cases} -\Delta p - k^2 p = 0 & \text{in } \Omega, \\ \frac{\partial p}{\partial \mathbf{n}} = -\frac{\partial L_{\mathbf{x}_0}}{\partial \mathbf{n}} & \text{on } \Gamma, \end{cases} \quad (19)$$

Figure 5: Rectangular domain: Error curves for the fifth eigenvalue. Triangular meshes on the left and quadrilateral meshes on the right.

Figure 6: Interior car domain, meshed with quadrilateral elements.

where $L_{\mathbf{x}_0}$ is the fundamental solution centered in \mathbf{x}_0 , $L_{\mathbf{x}_0} = \frac{i}{4} H_0^{(1)}(k | \mathbf{x} - \mathbf{x}_0 |)$ [4]. It is easy to verify that the solution of (19) is $p = -L_{\mathbf{x}_0}$. Thus, we have set up a source problem with an arbitrary geometry of the boundary but know the exact solution. Therefore, we can easily evaluate the numerical error of our finite element technique. This type of error estimator has been described by Ochmann and Osetrov [16, 17].

The displacement formulation of this problem can be written as

$$\begin{cases} -\nabla(\operatorname{div}\mathbf{u}) - k^2\mathbf{u} = \mathbf{0} & \text{in } \Omega, \\ \mathbf{u} \cdot \mathbf{n} = -\frac{1}{\omega^2\rho_0} \frac{\partial L_{x_0}}{\partial \mathbf{n}} & \text{on } \Gamma. \end{cases} \quad (20)$$

The domain is meshed with quadrilateral elements for two different refinements. We compute the relative percental error for pressure and displacement,

$$er_p = \frac{\|p_{ex} - p\|_{0,\Omega}}{\|p_{ex}\|_{0,\Omega}} \cdot 100\%, \quad er_u = \frac{\|\mathbf{u}_{ex} - \mathbf{u}\|_{0,\Omega}}{\|\mathbf{u}_{ex}\|_{0,\Omega}} \cdot 100\%. \quad (21)$$

This means that, if we solve (19) obtaining an approximation of p , we use (6) for having an approximation of \mathbf{u} .

Figure 7 shows the error curve for quadrilateral elements. In the left subfigure, the error is computed for the pressure, whereas the right subfigure shows the error for the displacement.

Figure 7: Interior car domain: Quadrilateral meshes. Error for the pressure on the left and for the displacement on the right.

For the error computation in pressure, Lagrangian elements give significantly better results than Raviart-Thomas elements. This is most likely due to the fact that evaluation of the sound pressure in the displacement formulation requires an additional differentiation of the directly computed displacement results to determine the divergence.

If the error is computed in displacements, \mathbf{RT}_1 gives better results than P_1 , while P_2 is nearly

identical to \mathbf{RT}_2 and third order Lagrangian elements are slightly better than third order Raviart-Thomas elements. Compared to the sound pressure results, the performance of Raviart-Thomas elements is much better, most likely since the differentiation is now required to determine the gradient of the sound pressure in the pressure formulation.

5. Three-dimensional examples

5.1. Eigenvalues in a parallelepipedical domain

The first of our three-dimensional test cases considers the spectral problem of a closed rectangular parallelepipedical domain, analogously to the rectangular domain in Section 4.1.

Again, for the boundary condition $\frac{\partial p}{\partial \mathbf{n}} = 0$ on Γ , the exact eigenvalues can be computed analytically as

$$\omega_{lmn} = c_0 \pi \sqrt{\left(\frac{l}{L_x}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{m}{L_y}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{n}{L_z}\right)^2} \quad \text{rad/s} \quad \text{with } l, m, n = 0, 1, 2, \dots,$$

where L_x , L_y , and L_z are the edge lengths of the domain.

For our computations, we choose a domain with lengths $L_x = 1\text{m}$, $L_y = 1.2\text{m}$, and $L_z = 0.8\text{m}$. Again, air accounts for the acoustic fluid. Due to computational reasons, only first and second order elements have been used. Tetrahedral and hexahedral element shapes are used.

In Figures 8 and 9 we show the relative percental error, (18), for the fourth and the fifth eigenvalues, respectively. These modes account for the 001-mode ($l = 0, m = 0, n = 1$) and the 110-mode.

The results shown in Figures 8 and 9 indicate that Raviart-Thomas elements perform better than Lagrangian elements on tetrahedral meshes while Lagrangian elements provide lower errors than Raviart-Thomas elements on hexahedral meshes.

5.2. Duct problem

The duct problem considers a rectangular parallelepipedic domain again. The domain is limited to the interval of $(-a, a) \times (-b, b) \times (-c, c)$, but, in this case, the dimension a is significantly larger

Figure 8: Rectangular parallelepipedal domain: Error curves for the fourth eigenvalue. Tetrahedral meshes on the left and hexahedral meshes on the right.

Figure 9: Rectangular parallelepipedal domain: Error curves for the fifth eigenvalue. Tetrahedral meshes on the left and hexahedral meshes on the right.

than the other two (see Figure 10). We consider the problem

$$\begin{cases} -\Delta p - k^2 p = 0 & \text{in } \Omega, \\ \frac{\partial p}{\partial \mathbf{n}} = i k e^{i \mathbf{k} \cdot \mathbf{x}} & \text{on } x_1 = -a \text{ or } x_1 = a, \\ \frac{\partial p}{\partial \mathbf{n}} = 0 & \text{on the rest of the boundary,} \end{cases}$$

for $\mathbf{k} := (k, 0, 0)$. It is easy to see that this problem can be reduced to a 1D Helmholtz problem, and, then, we can compute its exact solution with [12]

$$p_{ex}(\mathbf{x}) = e^{i\mathbf{k}\cdot\mathbf{x}}, \quad \mathbf{u}_{ex}(\mathbf{x}) = \frac{1}{\rho_0\omega^2}i\mathbf{k}e^{i\mathbf{k}\cdot\mathbf{x}}.$$

This solution can be understood as a traveling wave. For this wave, the magnitude of the sound pressure is constant everywhere in the duct and only the phase angle varies. This makes it an excellent test case for the performance of numerical methods for the Helmholtz equation as shown in [12, 13, 14].

We use $a = 4\text{ m}$, $b = 0.5\text{ m}$, and $c = 0.5\text{ m}$, with air inside, and $\omega = 100\text{ rad/s}$. In Figure 10 the real and the imaginary part of the solution are shown.

Figure 10: Duct problem: Real part (left) and imaginary part (right) of the solution.

Figure 11 presents the convergence behaviour for tetrahedral elements, showing, in the left subfigure, the relative percental error for the pressure and, in the right subfigure, the relative percental error for the displacement, according to (21). Analogously, Figure 12 shows results for hexahedral meshes.

For tetrahedral meshes, Lagrangian elements always produce better results. It can be noticed, that, if the error is computed based on displacements, Lagrangian elements perform only slightly better than Raviart-Thomas elements.

When hexahedral meshes are used, Lagrangian elements perform better as long as the error is computed for the pressure. If the error is computed on the basis of the displacement results, then, Raviart-Thomas elements return better results.

Figure 11: Duct problem: Convergence behaviour for tetrahedral elements, error computed in pressure (left) and in displacements (right).

Figure 12: Duct problem: Convergence behaviour for hexahedral elements, error computed in pressure (left) and in displacements (right).

5.3. Computation of eigenvalues in a domain representing the interior of a bus

The final computational example which is considered in this article regards a non-academic case for which the exact solution is unknown. A three-dimensional mesh is built by using a CAD data of an urban bus (see Figure 13). The first five non-zero eigenvalues and eigenvectors are evaluated and presented. Figure 14 shows these eigenvectors.

Table 1 presents the eigenvalues which are obtained from the tetrahedral mesh for different

Figure 13: Urban bus: Mesh of the interior domain.

Figure 14: Urban bus: First five eigenvectors associated to non-zero eigenvalues.

types of elements. We remark that the (unknown) eigenvalues of the problem are approached from different directions: while Lagrangian elements for the pressure formulation overestimate the exact eigenvalues, Raviart-Thomas elements used in the displacement formulation underestimate these

pressure			displacement		
P_1	P_2	P_3	RT_1	RT_2	EV
19136	133679	430129	181907	805218	dof
132.230596	131.952570	131.929532	131.710982	131.886263	ω_1
242.236481	241.286264	241.225023	240.578223	241.110562	ω_2
394.575208	392.896303	392.838374	392.146819	392.736640	ω_3
463.236774	460.615308	460.503875	459.442122	460.304400	ω_4
489.231423	486.637513	486.565707	485.707889	486.445000	ω_5

Table 1: Urban bus: Eigenvalues for $c_0 = 340 \frac{m}{s}$ with tetrahedral elements.

values. Moreover, as observed in the test in Section 5.1, \mathbf{RT}_1 gives better results than P_1 elements.

6. CONCLUSIONS

In this paper we have presented the solution of the Helmholtz differential equation for the spectral and the source problem. This solution is achieved by two different formulations by using, respectively, the sound pressure and the displacement as primal variables. The first one is discretized by means of standard Lagrangian elements while for the second one Raviart-Thomas elements have been used in order to avoid spurious modes.

Comparison of both formulations can be summarized as follows:

- Spectral problems. In these cases, we have compared the first 5 eigenvalues in each case. Lagrangian elements gave better results than Raviart-Thomas for quadrilateral (in 2d examples) and hexahedral (3d examples) meshes. When triangular and tetrahedral meshes are used, Raviart-Thomas elements have provided better results for order 1 and 2, while for order 3 the pressure formulation with Lagrangian elements provides better. Convergence rates of elements of the same order become similar.

It is also important to remark that, with Raviart-Thomas elements, the results are better for triangular meshes than for quadrilateral ones, it is, for a given number of degrees of freedom, the error is smaller if the mesh is made by triangular elements. Lagrangian elements work in the opposite way, it is, quadrilateral meshes are preferable.

- Source problems. In the source problems, the error of the results was computed for the pressure as well as for the displacements. Only in the case of quadrilateral and hexahedral elements and when the error was computed for the displacements, Raviart-Thomas elements

give better results than Lagrangian elements. When triangular and tetrahedral meshes were considered, Lagrangian elements performed better for both, pressure and displacements.

Regarding these results, we can say that in most cases, Lagrangian elements give better results than Raviart-Thomas elements, as expected. Therefore, when it is possible to choose between the pressure or the displacement formulation for the Helmholtz problem, the former, discretized with Lagrangian elements, is preferable. There are only two cases in which Raviart-Thomas elements give better results: in the case of complex three-dimensional models, where low-order Raviart-Thomas elements solve the spectral problem more accurately, and when the source problem has to be solved by using quadrilateral or hexahedral finite elements and we are interested in computing the displacements.

The use of Raviart-Thomas elements, however, can be useful when considering coupled problems such as fluid-structure interaction problems or the coupling between a pure displacement formulation in aeroacoustics with regions without flow.

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